

The Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration – Paving the road for a Helmholtz FAIR data space

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Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration

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HMC Mission and Vision

Mission

- Turn FAIR into reality in Helmholtz
- Connecting the distributed Helmholtz research data ecosystem

Vision

- Create a sustainable, distributed, semantically enriched Helmholtz FAIR data space.

The FAIR data space is a "decentralized infrastructure for trustworthy data sharing and exchange in data ecosystems based on **commonly agreed principles**"
(Nagel L., Lycklama D., 2021)

HMC in a nutshell

8 HMC Units
(Aeronautics, Space & Transport, Earth & Environment, Energy, Health, Information, Matter, FAIR Data Commons, HMC Office)
at 6 Helmholtz host centres

Stakeholders addressed by HMC

data producers, repository managers, data curator, data re-users & software developers, ...

HMC Activities

State of FAIR

Community
Surveys

FAIR
Assessment

Information
Portal

Data Connectivity

Metadata
Tools

FAIR
Digital Object
Implementation

Helmholtz
Knowledge
Graph

Community Implementation

Training &
Events

Guidelines &
Recommen-
dations

Community
Projects &
Processes

Sneak peak into our HMC results

State of FAIR

Community Survey

FAIR Assessment

Information Portal

Data Connectivity

Metadata Tools

FDO Implementation

Connecting Data

Community Implementation

Trainings & Events

Guidelines & Recommendations

HMC Projects

36 funded since 2020

Community Processes

Community Survey - Helmholtz Data Professionals Survey 2024

Target group: Helmholtz Data Professionals

Goals

- Identify data professionals in Helmholtz
- Assess state of RDM practices
- Analyse gaps and needs – action items for HMC

Results (156 reponses):

- RDM in Helmholtz performed by multiple stakeholders across professions
- data publishing alignment with selected FAIR data principles by 1/3 to 2/3 of participants
- High interest in diverse service formats
- Obstacles regarding RDM-related work: Lack of resources (82 %), technical knowledge (42%), technical infrastructure (38 %) and technical solutions (34 %).

Job title of participants

TOP 5 service formats

HMC Projects – involving the community

Turning FAIR recommendations & concepts into application level

- **HELIPORT**: developed a platform to create a more FAIR & comprehensible project workflow description
- **Software CaRD**: build a portable, non-centralized graphical software dashboard to support curation and approval of software
- **FAIR WISH**: developed SAMIRA software tool for automated registration workflow of IGSNs (International Generic Sample Number)

Implementing project results into existing data systems & infrastructure within Helmholtz & beyond

Conclusion and HMC outlook activities

State of FAIR

	Community Surveys	Publication of survey results
	FAIR Assessment	
	Information Portal	

Data Connectivity

	Metadata Tools	Further development of tools and services
	FAIR Digital Object Implementation	Working on bridging concepts
	Helmholtz Knowledge Graph	

Community Implementation

	Training & Events	New trainings & events preparation
	Guidelines & Recommendations	Next call for projects March 2025
	Community Projects & Processes	

Our upcoming HMC events

Fourth HMC Conference ...

... AND the first time in-person

Three days all about Metadata!

More information:

<https://www.helmholtz-metadaten.de/hmc-conference-2025>

Join our next HMC FAIR Fridays on...

- Relevance of provenance in the context of FAIR (21 February)
- A FAIR-enabling resource for biodiversity monitoring schemes (21 March)
- Creative Commons licences & FAIR data (04 April)

More information:

<https://helmholtz-metadaten.de/en/fair-friday>

Thank you for your attention

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